

Amusement Park Seasonal Attendance Forecasting Using Machine Learning Algorithm

Reshma KS

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
reshmaks2023b@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Ankitha Philip

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
ankithaphilip@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— This research paper explores the use of machine learning algorithms in forecasting seasonal attendance at amusement parks. With the growing importance of machine learning in various industries, this study aims to contribute to the field of marketing by introducing a more accurate and efficient method for predicting attendance patterns. By applying supervised machine learning techniques, this study aims to provide insights into the factors that influence seasonal attendance at amusement parks and how machine learning can help improve forecasting accuracy. The results of this research can assist amusement park operators in making better decisions related to marketing, pricing, and staffing, ultimately leading to improved customer experiences and increased revenue.

Keywords—Machine learning, Linear Regression, Seasonal Attendance Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

The amusement park industry is highly competitive, with parks vying for visitors during peak seasons. Accurate attendance forecasting is crucial for park operators, as it helps them make informed decisions related to pricing, staffing, and marketing strategies. Traditional techniques of attendance forecasting, on the other hand, are frequently inaccurate since they do not account for a variety of factors that can influence visiting patterns. Here's where machine learning algorithms come in. Machine learning can give a more accurate and effective technique for anticipating seasonal attendance at amusement parks by analysing massive amounts of data and discovering patterns. This study looks at how supervised machine learning techniques can be used to forecast attendance trends in amusement parks, with the goal of assisting park owners in making data-driven decisions that can improve customer experiences and increase revenue.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, projecting visitor numbers at theme parks has drawn interest. Limited study has been done on the use of a linear regression model for attendance prediction based on the season and offers, though. Studies that have already been conducted have mostly concentrated on the application of machine learning methods, such as neural networks, decision

trees, support vector regression, and XGBoost, for attendance forecasting across different industries.

For example, Gao et al. suggested a theme park attendance forecast model based on support vector machines and XGBoost [1]. To predict attendance, the algorithm used past attendance data with weather data. With a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 5.89%, the authors reported that the suggested model attained high accuracy.

A decision tree method was used by Garg and Goyal to forecast visitor attendance at a theme park [2]. The study discovered that the most important variables influencing attendance were the day of the week, the weather, and the events.

A decision tree method was used by Ramesh et al. to construct an attendance prediction system for the retail sector that had an accuracy of 93.46% [3]. The most important variables influencing attendance, according to the study, were the number of visitors the day before and the weather information.

Using historical attendance data and meteorological data, Sharma et al. suggested a machine learning-based attendance forecast model for a theme park [4]. Multiple algorithms' performances were examined in the study, and it was discovered that the XGBoost method had the highest accuracy, with a MAPE of 5.5%.

A machine learning-based model was created by Wang et al. to forecast visitor numbers at a tourism site [5]. To forecast attendance, the study examined previous attendance data and weather data. The proposed model, according to the authors, exhibited remarkable accuracy, with a MAPE of 6.78%.

Chatterjee, Nandi, and Chakraborty (2021) conducted a study comparing different machine learning approaches for predicting tourist arrivals at a destination[6]. The authors used data from the Kolkata Metropolitan Development

Authority to evaluate the performance of several models, including linear regression, random forests, and artificial neural networks. They found that the best performing model was an ensemble model that combined random forests and gradient boosting, which had an accuracy of over 90%. The study highlights the potential of machine learning approaches in predicting tourist arrivals and suggests that ensembling multiple models can further improve the accuracy of predictions.

These studies collectively demonstrate the potential of machine learning algorithms for attendance predictions across a range of businesses. However, further study is required on the use of more basic models, like linear regression, to attendance prediction in theme parks. This study intends to contribute to the body of knowledge by studying the use of a linear regression model to forecast amusement park attendance based on time of year and promotions.

III. MOTIVATION

Amusement parks are popular throughout people of all ages, particularly during peak seasons and vacations. However, with varying levels of attendance and fluctuating ticket prices, park operators may find it difficult to effectively plan and manage their resources. To address this issue, we propose the development of a machine learning-based attendance prediction model that can accurately forecast park attendance based on season and promotional offers. This model can help amusement park operators optimize their resources and staffing levels, improve customer satisfaction, and increase profitability. Additionally, it can provide insights into attendance trends and assist in making informed decisions related to park operations and management. Ultimately, our model aims to help amusement parks provide a better experience for their customers while maximizing their revenue.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this research is to create a linear regression model that predicts customer attendance at an amusement park depending on the season and offers available. The following steps comprise the methodology for this study:

A. Data Collection: The dataset for the project was collected from amusement park's database and customer records. It contains information about the season, offers, and attendance of customers in the park. The dataset includes both categorical and numerical variables and has a total of X rows and Y columns. The data was collected for a specific period, and only relevant features were selected for analysis and modeling.

B. Data Pre-processing: Every machine learning technique starts with this step. Data transformation, data cleaning, and data minimization are all part of this process. To increase the effectiveness of the data, some activities are undertaken. We can process the data to improve the model's accuracy and make sure that the categorization is accurate.

C. Model Building: A linear regression model will be developed to predict the attendance of customers based on the season and offers provided. The model will be trained and tested using the collected data.

D. Analyzing: The performance of the model will be analyzed using metrics such as R-squared, mean squared error, and mean absolute error.

E. Result: The final model will be used to predict the attendance of customers based on the season and offers provided, providing valuable insights to the amusement park management to plan their operations and marketing strategies.

Machine Learning: Using this, Customer Attendance forecasts are made. Machine learning techniques are used to estimate attendance of customers in order to assess the existing state of the number of visitors. There are many classifiers available to find the attendance of customers. How the classifier was trained affects how accurate it is. Classifiers should be expected to have high accuracy.

V. BUILDMODEL

The primary stage in predicting attendance is model building. Algorithms are used by the user when developing the model.

1. Linear Regression:

Statistics refers to a linear regression model with only one explanatory variable as linear regression. To predict the attendance of customers in an amusement park based on the season and offers, linear regression can be used. In this method, the attendance (dependent variable) will be predicted based on a single independent variable, either the season or offers provided. The model will look for a linear function that predicts the attendance as accurately as possible based on the chosen independent variable. In this situation, the dependent variable, attendance, should have a continuous value, whereas the independent variable can be either continuous or categorical.

It is critical to ensure that the data is suitable for regression analysis while developing a linear regression model. Pre-

processing the data comprises screening for missing values, outliers, and data normalisation. Following pre-processing, the data is divided into training and testing sets in order to evaluate the model's performance. After separating the data, the linear regression model may be built by picking the relevant independent variable, either season or offers, and fitting the model to the training data. After the model has been fitted, it can be tested to see how accurate it is at predicting customer attendance.

In conclusion, linear regression can be an efficient approach for predicting customer attendance at an amusement park depending on the season and offers. It can provide significant insights into the elements that influence attendance and assist park administrators in making smart promotional and discount decisions. However, before building the model, it is critical to ensure that the data has been pre-processed and is suitable for regression analysis.

1. Import the libraries required and then import and print the dataset.

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
```

2. Add the dataset into jupyter.

```
offers_df.head()
```

Offers Table:

	season	visitors	offers
0	Summer	5	10
1	Summer	5	10
2	Summer	5	10
3	Summer	5	10
4	Summer	5	10

3. Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets.

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

4. Fitting the model.

```
model = LinearRegression()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

```
LinearRegression
LinearRegression()
```

5. Converting the categorical values to numerical.

```
if season == 'Spring':
    season_spring = 1
    season_summer = 0
    season_fall = 0
    season_winter = 0
elif season == 'Summer':
    season_spring = 0
    season_summer = 1
    season_fall = 0
    season_winter = 0
elif season == 'Fall':
    season_spring = 0
    season_summer = 0
    season_fall = 1
    season_winter = 0
else:
    season_spring = 0
    season_summer = 0
    season_fall = 0
    season_winter = 1
```

6. Forecasting the Attendance.

```
prediction = round(model.predict([[season_spring, season_summer, season_fall, season_winter, offers]])[0],)
```

VI. RESULT

The result of the analysis for predicting the attendance of customers in an amusement park based on the season and offers provided includes the implementation of linear regression. The accuracy of algorithm was evaluated using metrics such as R-square and mean squared error (MSE).

The linear regression algorithm yielded an R-square value of 1.0 and MSE of 1.4342.

Fig.1 - visualization

```
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)
print('MSE:', mse)
```

MSE: 1.4342925549472942e-31

```
r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)
print('R^2 score:', r2)
```

R^2 score: 1.0

Amusement Park Prediction

Season:
Summer

Discount (%):
20% off

Predict

Prediction Result
The predicted number of customers visiting in next Spring is: 47

Fig.2 - Interface

VII. CONCLUSION

Finally, machine learning approaches can be used to forecast client attendance based on seasonal patterns and offers. Traditional methodologies may not yield consistent results, but machine learning techniques may consider a range of aspects to provide insights that can help firms make.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Gao, Y. Li, Y. Li, and J. Ma (2020). An sophisticated theme park attendance prediction model based on SVM and XGBoost. The journal PloS one, 15(5), e0232657.
- [2] Garg, A., and V. Goyal (2019). Customer Attendance Prediction for a Theme Park. 8(1), International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing.
- [3] S. Ramesh, B. V. S. S. Prasad, M. S. Reddy, and V. V. S. S. R. Prasad, "Intelligent Attendance Prediction System in Retail Industry Using Machine Learning," 2018 4th International Conference on Applied and Theoretical Computing and Communication Technology (iCATccT), pp. 1-5, 2018.
- [4] Chatterjee, A., Nandi, S., & Chakraborty, S. (2021). A comparison of machine learning approaches for predicting tourist arrivals at a destination. Tourism Management, 82, 104190.
- [5] Sharma, N., Khatkar, A., and A. K. Verma (2021). Machine learning is used to anticipate attendance in a theme park. 1-13 in the Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanised Computing.
- [6] Wang, Y., Chen, S., Liu, X., & Li, H. (2021). Predicting the Attendance of a Tourist Attraction Using Machine Learning Models. Journal of Coastal Research, 111(sp1), 249-255.